

Engineering a Knowledge Graph to improve the data-driven study of the impact of human recreational activities in the French Alps

Bénédicte Bucher¹, Vanessa Pech¹, and Marie-Dominique Van Damme¹

¹University Gustave Eiffel, IGN-Geodata Paris, LASTIG, Champs sur Marne, France

Correspondence: Bénédicte Bucher (benedicte.bucher@ign.fr)

Abstract. Scientific observatories of the French Alps need to accurately represent human recreational outdoor activities in order to understand their impacts. We present work in progress on co-designing a knowledge graph about data and processes relevant to studying these human activities and their impact on ecosystems.

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well as important areas. Raw data must be processed to achieve the correct spatial, temporal, and thematic granularity — ranging from system-wide to site-specific, and from individual to collective scales — in order to correlate human activities with animal behaviour and habitats, compare situations across locations or over time, detect conflicts, and identify land-sharing strategies. While some of this expertise is available through explicit online documentation, much of it can only be acquired through exchanges with the data provider or collaboration between scientists from different communities, such as ecologists and geographic information scientists.

1 Studying the impact of human activities in the French Alps

The French Alps are heavily affected by the climate crisis and undergo more rapid change than the plains. In order to protect them, it is crucial to develop a better understanding of the various dynamics at play and their interdependencies (Edoardo et al., 2019). To this end, scientific observatories and communities collect data on fauna and flora, for example from GPS collars or field surveys, and analyse it to identify sensitive areas or other key features to inform action. With the rapid increase in human outdoor activities such as the renowned Ultra-trail Mont Blanc, it is essential to accurately represent this anthropogenic pressure in order to make informed decisions that promote more sustainable activities.

Although there is data on human recreational outdoor activities in the French Alps, it is highly scattered, making it challenging to discover and reuse properly. It is necessary to know who publishes what data, under what conditions it can be accessed, how to correctly interpret a set of observations and prepare them for advanced spatial and temporal analysis, and how to extract meaningful information about movements and states, as

2 A Knowledge Graph approach

The INTFOROUT research project brings together ecologists and GI scientists to study the impact of human recreational activities on ecosystems in the French Alps. One of the project's objectives is to design a collaborative and open Knowledge Graph to encode and articulate the expertise about available data and procedures held by the project participants. This will provide the explicit semantics needed to enhance the re-usability of data, as emphasised by Janowicz et al. (2020). The participants each hold different expertise on data about humans or fauna. The purpose of the KG is to facilitate the sharing of this expertise during the project and with future users outside the consortium.

We present work in progress on co-designing a KG about data and processes relevant to studying human activities and their impact on French Alps ecosystems. The co-designers are INTFOROUT participants who are considered both as contributors to specific parts of the KG and as future beneficiaries of it. One challenge is motivating them and enabling them to contribute meaningfully to the KG design and production. Our approach involves designing a pilot prototype that

Figure 1. Overview of the different categories of nodes and edges of KG-POC.

showcases the KG’s relevance in the project context and associating the KG with a companion environment which makes it easier for participants to manipulate.

This poster presents our pilot prototype : the KG classes and instances, and the companion environment which is named *Sham-Wah*, after the French name for the ibex.

3 Core structure and first instances

The use case to inform the design of the pilot has been selected with the INTFOROUT participants. The aim is to answer the question : "what data are available about human activities in our areas of interest, Chamonix and Les Bauges". The core structure of the KG is illustrated in Fig. 1. Some items refer to the phenomena of interest to the project (e.g. the concept of human activity) while others refer to available digital assets, which are described as catalogued resources. A property *represents* expresses the connection between an asset and a concept for which it provides a (possibly partial) view.

To expand the scope of data that can be retrieved based on the use case question, the *affords* property is introduced to express the capacity of a LandEntity to support an Activity, after Gibson (1977). For example, some paths afford cycling. We manually create instances of Datasets for a variety of data that can be obtained from private companies and leisure-oriented associations, including datasets that are not visible on any public portal. To explicitly express the semantics of the bibliography paper by Van Damme et al. (2024), the concept of *PopulationFootprint* is introduced as a specific *LandEntity*.

4 The KG companion *Sham-Wah*

Sham-Wah is a KG companion that has been developed to demonstrate the benefits of the KG. In this pilot, it is used to discover data about human activities. A query panel presents the predefined query “data about human activities” as illustrated in 2. Retrieved datasets are presented in a list, along with other recommended assets. When a user selects an item in the list, the corresponding node is displayed in the exploration panel, together with other Cataloged Resources (Dataset, Dataservice, Process, Paper, UserFeedback) that are linked to it. Additional properties are accessible via a pop-up panel. More generally, *Sham-Wah* helps participants to understand the KG well enough to contribute to the production of new instances and to be consulted for the creation of new classes and properties.

4.1 First evaluation

A qualitative study was conducted to introduce the KG pilot to INTFOROUT participants. Participants could understand concrete benefits from a KG better through this pilot than through theoretical presentations. They assessed that the retrieved assets were relevant to the query. Introducing local ad hoc items in the KG, that are aligned with different domain-specific vocabularies is an effective way to focus on the structure of knowledge specific to the project, while avoiding complex philosophical questions. User feedback is an important class element of the KG because it provides perspectives on assets with a shared focus and it can be edited very simply as free text, provided at least one target is cited. Participants expressed the need for more description of the temporal aspect of data, as well as conceptual schema and licensing.

Ongoing work focuses on further evaluation of the pilot and extending the KG to integrate more nodes related to data about animals, as well as co-specifying maps that will answer the ecologists questions.

4.2 Data and Software Availability Section

The developed knowledge graph and software *Sham-Wah* are published under a permissive CC-BY-SA 4.0 license and available at <https://github.com/IntForOut>.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that the only Generative AI tools used in preparing this manuscript were DeepL and ChatGPT, for assistance with English writing.

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Figure 2. Sham-Wah interface to showcase the retrieval of data about human activities in the KG-POC

Project: Multisource spatial data INTegration FOR the Monitoring of Ecosystems under the pressure of OUTdoor recreation).

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